

Data Extraction Protocol and Guide

Systematic Review: A Systematic Review of Fuzzy Multimodal Emotion Recognition in Social Robotics

Version: 3.0 (Feb 2026) — Gold Standard (incl. Q1–Q9 quality checklist) — aligned with OSF protocol v2.1

1) Purpose and scope

This guide standardizes how reviewers extract data from included studies. It defines required fields, formatting rules, and quality checks so the final dataset is complete, consistent, and analysis-ready.

Extraction records what the study reports. Do not infer missing values and do not compute derived metrics during extraction. If something is unclear, document briefly in Reviewer_Comments and code the field as NR (Not Reported) or NA (Not Applicable).

Scope note (v2.1): Social robotics / HRI is not a hard inclusion gate at screening. Contextual HRI/robot information is captured here to support predefined subgroup analyses and the CORE vs EXTENDED stratification.

Important (v2.1): Quality assessment uses a 9-item checklist (Q1–Q9). To avoid a second full pass, Q1–Q9 are scored during extraction and the total is computed afterward.

2) Files, tools, and roles

- Master file (authoritative): /analysis/extraction/extraction_master_v3.0.xlsx
- Working copies: one per extractor (extraction_WORKING_<initials>_v3.0.xlsx), then merged into the master by the lead analyst
- Software: Microsoft Excel 365 (primary). Optional: Google Sheets for collaboration snapshots (never becomes the authoritative master)
- Record storage: PDFs of included studies in /analysis/full_text/ with stable filenames matching FirstAuthor_Year
- Template requirement: the master sheet must contain explicit columns for Q1–Q9 plus Quality_Total (0–18). If missing, insert Q1–Q9 immediately before Quality_Total.

Roles:

- Primary extractor: doctoral candidate (extracts all included studies unless split is agreed).
- Verifier: one supervisor re-extracts a random 20–25% subset for reliability checking (assigned by the lead).
- Lead analyst: computes agreement statistics, performs reconciliation, cleans the data, and locks the final master (not the extractors).

3) General coding rules

- Verbatim vs normalized: copy verbatim where specified; otherwise use the controlled vocabularies defined below.
- Missing / not applicable: use NR (Not Reported) and NA (Not Applicable). Never leave required cells blank unless explicitly stated.
- Numbers: use dot decimals (0.875). Record rates as proportions (0.923), not percentages (92.3%). Do not include the % sign.
- Dates: ISO-8601 (YYYY-MM-DD) when needed.
- Multiple items in one cell: separate with semicolons and a space (;).
- Direct quotes: wrap short quotes in double quotes and add a locator when possible (e.g., p. 3; Section 2.1). Keep quotes short.
- Units: record exactly as reported if non-standard; note any unit issues in Reviewer_Comments.
- No derived metrics: do not compute F1, RMSE, effect sizes, or averages. If a confusion matrix is provided, capture it verbatim in Outcome_Notes.
- Primary metric rule: if multiple metrics are reported, store one as Primary_Metric and list the rest in Other_Metrics (see Section D).
- One paper = one row: extract the primary fuzzy multimodal MER system as the main record; capture additional variants/ablations in Outcome_Notes.
- Quality checklist scoring: Q1–Q9 are scored as 2 (Yes), 1 (Partially), or 0 (No/Not Reported). Do not leave Q-items blank.

4) Field-by-field instructions (column order)

This list mirrors the columns in extraction_master_v3.0.xlsx. Example entries are illustrative.

A. Publication metadata

A1. FirstAuthor_Year

Format: Surname et al., YYYY (e.g., Chen et al., 2018).

A2. Title

Copy verbatim.

A3. Venue

Journal or conference name as printed.

A4. DOI_or_URL

DOI preferred (plain string, no https://doi.org/). If only a stable URL exists, record the full URL.

A5. Funding

Copy verbatim or NR. If explicitly “no funding”, record “None declared”.

B. Study characteristics

B1. Stated_Objective

Copy one concise verbatim sentence (≤ 2 lines) summarizing the stated aim; include a locator when possible.

B2. Datasets_Used

List dataset names exactly as reported (e.g., IEMOCAP; RAVDESS; DEAP; custom). If custom, add “custom” plus a short description in B2_Notes.

B2_Notes

Free text notes for custom datasets, acquisition details, or dataset mapping notes.

B3. Dataset_Type

Controlled vocabulary: Public / Proprietary / Mixed.

B4. Sample_Size

If original data collection: numeric total participants. If benchmark only: record dataset subject count as reported. Use NR if not stated. Clarify ambiguity in B4_Notes.

B4_Notes

Clarify whether B4 refers to participants collected vs benchmark subjects; note any missing details.

B5. Language_Context

E.g., English; Mandarin; Multilingual; NR.

B6. Study_Setting_Context

Controlled vocabulary: Laboratory/Controlled; Real-world/In the wild; Simulation; Mixed; NR.

Use “Mixed” if both lab and in-the-wild components are present.

C. Emotion-recognition system (the intervention)

C1. Input_Modalities

Controlled vocabulary (use any that apply; specify physiology type):

Speech; Face; Body; Text; Physiology-EEG; Physiology-ECG; Physiology-EMG; Physiology-GSR; Physiology-EDA; Physiology-PPG; Physiology-Respiration; Context; Other (specify in C1_Notes).

C1_Notes

If “Other”, specify the modality (e.g., thermal; depth; eye gaze). Note sensor/wearable names if relevant.

C2. Emotion_Model

Choose one: Ekman-6; Plutchik; Valence-Arousal; Other dimensional; Discrete-custom; Custom (describe briefly in C2_Notes).

C2_Notes

Briefly describe label set if custom (e.g., 8 emotions; 3 arousal levels).

C3. Feature_Extraction_By_Modality

Free text, concise and structured by modality. Example:

Audio: MFCC, spectrogram; Video: CNN (ResNet-18); Text: BERT; Physiology: HRV features.

C4. Fuzzy_Component_Type

Choose one: Mamdani; Takagi-Sugeno; ANFIS; Fuzzy layer (DL); Fuzzy rule base; Fuzzy integrals (e.g., Choquet/Sugeno integral); Fuzzy c-means (within inference); Type-2 fuzzy; Other (specify in C4_Notes).

C4_Notes

If fuzzy c-means is used purely for clustering with no inference/fusion role, note that explicitly. Do not infer eligibility; just document what the authors state.

C5. Fuzzy_Component_Role

Choose one or multiple (separate with ;):

Classifier; Fusion engine; Feature weighting/selection; Decision rule; Uncertainty handling; Rule learning/optimization; Other (specify in C5_Notes).

C5_Notes

Briefly explain the role if it is not obvious from the vocabulary.

C6. Fusion_Strategy

Choose one: Early/feature-level; Late/decision-level; Hybrid; Hierarchical.

If a named method is stated, append in parentheses (e.g., Late (stacking); Hybrid (EmbraceNet)).

C7. Missing_Modality_Handling

Choose one: Described / Not described.

If Described, summarize briefly (e.g., modality dropout; gating; rule-based fallback; imputation).

C8. Baseline_or_Comparator_Within_Study

Choose: Yes; No; Partial.

If Yes/Partial, specify comparator types in C8_Notes (e.g., non-fuzzy ML baseline; unimodal ablation; fusion ablation; SOTA).

C8_Notes

Free text description of baselines/ablations used in the paper.

D. Outcomes and validation

D1. Primary_Metric

Record one main performance metric value as reported. If multiple metrics exist, prioritize:

Macro-F1 → Accuracy → task-appropriate primary metric (e.g., CCC for regression) as the primary.

Enter as a proportion to three decimals (e.g., 0.873). If authors report %, convert to proportion and note the original in Outcome_Notes.

D2. Other_Metrics

Semicolon-separated list as reported (e.g., Precision=0.84; Recall=0.86; RMSE=0.41). Use proportions for rates.

D3. Validation_Scheme

Choose one and give details: k-fold CV (k=10); LOSO; Train/Test (80/20); External test set; Nested CV; Other (specify).

D4. Split_Unit (if stated)

Choose: Subject-independent; Segment/frame-level; Session-level; Mixed; NR.

Definitions:

- Subject-independent: train and test sets contain different subjects (includes LOSO if stated).
- Segment/frame-level: random split of segments/frames without subject independence.
- Session-level: split by recording sessions; may or may not be subject-independent.
- Mixed: more than one split unit is used or reported.

If NR, keep NR and clarify ambiguity in Outcome_Notes or Reviewer_Comments.

D5. Validation_Setting

Choose one: Laboratory/Controlled; Simulation; Real-world/In the wild; Mixed; NR.

D6. Robot_or_Agent_Platform

E.g., Pepper; NAO; Social robot (unspecified); Virtual agent; Smartphone agent; None/NA.

If multiple platforms, list with semicolons.

D7. HRI_Context (for subgroup analysis; not a gate)

Choose: Yes; No; Unclear.

Yes only if the study explicitly evaluates in HRI, social robotics, or human-robot interaction contexts.

D8. Interaction_Setting (if HRI_Context=Yes or if stated)

Free text, concise. Example: "in-home assistance; lab interaction task; educational tutoring; customer service scenario". Use NR if not stated.

D9. Confusion_Matrix_or_Outputs

Paste a compact representation if given (e.g., matrix or per-class table); do not compute anything. Use Outcome_Notes to include page/section pointers.

Outcome_Notes

Free text: capture author phrasing, per-class values, tables/figures references, page/section locators, and any caveats.

E. Reproducibility and quality appraisal (v2.1)

E1. Open_Code_or_Data

Choose: Code yes/no; Data yes/no.

If links are provided, include them in E1_Notes.

E1_Notes

Record repository name or URL and any access notes (e.g., "available upon request").

E2. Reproducibility_Details

Choose: Sufficient; Partial; Insufficient; NR.

Use "Sufficient" only if method + data split/validation details + key hyperparameters or training setup are adequately described for conceptual replication.

E3. Reporting_Clarity

Choose: Yes; No; Partial (anchored to whether methods/results suffice for extraction and interpretation).

Quality checklist items (Q1–Q9)

Each item is scored as 2 (Yes), 1 (Partially), or 0 (No/Not Reported). Use a short note in Reviewer_Comments if an item is borderline.

Domain A: Reporting and reproducibility

Q1. Clear objectives/problem definition?

- 2: objective and problem framing are explicit and specific to MER.
- 1: objective exists but is vague or only indirectly stated.
- 0: objectives are absent or not interpretable.

Q2. Architecture described in sufficient detail (including fuzzy and fusion components)?

- 2: pipeline and fuzzy + fusion components are described clearly enough to follow implementation logic.
- 1: partial description; key components are missing/unclear.
- 0: insufficient architecture detail.

Q3. Dataset clearly identified and availability stated?

- 2: dataset(s) are clearly named/defined and availability is stated (public/proprietary/links).
- 1: dataset is described but naming/availability is incomplete.
- 0: dataset identification is unclear or absent.

Q4. Code or sufficiently detailed pseudo-code/algorithm description provided?

- 2: code link or detailed algorithm/pseudo-code is provided.
- 1: partial algorithmic detail but not enough for conceptual replication.
- 0: no code and insufficient algorithm detail.

Domain B: Methodological rigor

Q5. Emotion representation justified for the task/context?

- 2: emotion model/labels are justified (task, domain, theory, or data-driven rationale).
- 1: minimal or generic justification.
- 0: no justification.

Q6. Compared against at least one meaningful baseline/comparator?

- 2: at least one clear baseline/comparator (non-fuzzy, unimodal, ablation, or SOTA) is evaluated.
- 1: comparator exists but is weak/unclear or not meaningful.
- 0: no baseline/comparator.

Domain C: Validation and generalizability

Q7. Validation procedure appropriate and clearly described?

- 2: validation design is appropriate and clearly specified (e.g., subject-independent where relevant, clear CV/test strategy).
- 1: validation exists but key details are missing or appropriateness is uncertain.
- 0: validation is absent or not interpretable.

Q8. Metrics defined and appropriate for the task?

- 2: metrics are defined and appropriate; reported clearly.
- 1: metrics reported but definitions/appropriateness are unclear.
- 0: metrics are missing or not appropriate/usable.

Q9. Limitations discussed?

- 2: limitations are explicitly discussed (threats to validity, generalizability, data constraints).
- 1: limitations are mentioned superficially.
- 0: limitations are not discussed.

Quality_Total

Leave blank during extraction if the spreadsheet computes it automatically; otherwise the lead analyst will compute it as the sum of Q1–Q9 (range 0–18) after reconciliation. Do not compute totals manually if formulas exist.

F. Preregistered coding fields for synthesis stratification (v2.1)

These fields support the post-eligibility stratification of included studies into CORE versus EXTENDED for synthesis. Extractors should follow the rules below and avoid interpretation beyond what the paper states. If uncertain, code “Unclear” and add a brief note.

F1. TaskType

Controlled vocabulary: Emotion; Sentiment; Mixed (emotion + sentiment); Other; Unclear.

Use “Emotion” when target labels are emotions/affect states or dimensional affect (e.g., valence-arousal).

Use “Sentiment” for polarity/subjectivity targets.

Use “Mixed” if both are evaluated.

Use “Other” for affect-related tasks that are not strictly emotion or sentiment (e.g., stress detection, engagement, mood, cognitive load). Briefly specify the task in Reviewer_Comments.

F2. EmotionType

Controlled vocabulary: Discrete; Dimensional; Mixed; Unclear.

Discrete: categorical emotions (e.g., Ekman-6). Dimensional: valence/arousal (or similar). Mixed: both.

F3. FuzzyRole (synthesis-oriented)

Controlled vocabulary (multi-select with ;): Fusion; Classification; Decision; Uncertainty; Feature weighting/selection; Other; Unclear.

Difference from C5:

- C5 records the technical role as described by the authors (pipeline component role).
- F3 supports synthesis grouping and should usually mirror C5 in simpler labels (e.g., "Fusion engine" → Fusion; "Classifier" → Classification).

If the paper is ambiguous, prefer Unclear and add a one-line note; do not infer roles not stated or strongly implied by the described architecture.

F4. Evidence (for comparability)

Controlled vocabulary: Comparable performance; Performance reported (limited comparability); Methodological mapping only; Unclear.

- Comparable performance: extractable metrics with clear validation and an interpretable evaluation target (supports cross-study comparison within CORE).
- Performance reported (limited comparability): metrics exist but are difficult to compare across studies due to incompatible targets, missing reporting detail, or idiosyncratic validation.

Example: accuracy reported on a custom 3-emotion subset without clear split/validation details, making cross-study comparison unreliable.

- Methodological mapping only: included for mapping/context but not used for performance comparison tables by design.

If uncertain, code Unclear and explain briefly.

F5. CORE_vs_EXTENDED

Leave blank during extraction. The lead analyst assigns CORE/EXTENDED after extraction according to the preregistered rule set; extractors should not attempt to predict this classification.

G. Administrative fields

G1. Extractor_ID

Initials (e.g., SBG; AA; YC).

G2. Date_Extracted

YYYY-MM-DD.

G3. Reviewer_Comments

Free-text notes (ambiguities, oddities, page refs). Keep concise. Use this field to flag issues that may affect synthesis decisions or require lead review.

5) Workflow and QA steps

1. Pilot extraction (3–5 studies). Two reviewers independently extract the same small set, including Q1–Q9 scoring, then meet to harmonize interpretations and update this guide if needed.
2. Main extraction (single-reviewer pass). The primary extractor completes all remaining included studies following Sections 3–4.
3. Reliability check (random 20–25%). A supervisor independently re-extracts a random subset. The lead analyst computes agreement statistics (categorical: Cohen's κ ; ordinal 0/1/2 items such as Q1–Q9: weighted Cohen's κ recommended; numeric: ICC with a two-way random-effects, absolute agreement, single-rater specification). Suggested targets for the subset: $\kappa \geq 0.81$ and $ICC \geq 0.90$. Disagreements are logged and resolved; systematic errors trigger corrective sweeps.
4. Data cleaning. Lead analyst standardizes numeric formats, units, and categorical labels; verifies ranges/plausibility; and ensures NR/NA are used correctly. Quality_Total is computed from Q1–Q9 (range 0–18) after reconciliation.
5. Lock and archive. The finalized extraction_master_v3.0.xlsx is version-locked in OSF with a change note (ISO-8601 timestamp). Working files move to an /archive/ subfolder.

6) Decision rules (common edge cases)

- Unimodal focus inside included papers: if a paper includes both unimodal and multimodal experiments, extract the main fuzzy multimodal MER system; note unimodal baselines in Outcome_Notes.
- Fuzzy c-means only: if FCM is used purely for clustering with no inference/fusion role, document that explicitly in C4_Notes and C5_Notes (do not infer additional roles).
- Multiple experiments/models: extract the primary model aligned with fuzzy multimodal MER; list alternative models/ablations briefly in Outcome_Notes.
- Metric units: record rates as proportions; if authors report %, convert to proportion and note the original in Outcome_Notes.
- Multiple datasets: list all in B2; if outcomes differ by dataset, put the primary dataset's primary metric in D1 and describe the rest in Outcome_Notes.
- Missing data needed for synthesis: code NR and add a concise note in Reviewer_Comments. Any author-contact procedure is handled later by the lead team.
- Robot/HRI information: record D6–D8 as stated; do not infer HRI relevance if the paper does not explicitly present an HRI context.

- CORE vs EXTENDED assignment: do not assign during extraction; leave F5 blank. The lead analyst assigns CORE/EXTENDED post-extraction according to the preregistered rules. If any of F1–F4 are uncertain, code Unclear and flag it in Reviewer_Comments.
- Quality checklist borderline calls: if scoring Q-items is borderline, choose 1 (Partially) and add a short note in Reviewer_Comments with a locator.

7) Minimal extractor checklist (tick before marking a record “Done”)

- All required fields completed or coded NR/NA.
- Primary_Metric recorded as one value in proportion format (and extra details moved to Outcome_Notes).
- Feature extraction and fuzzy component captured clearly (C3–C5).
- Fusion strategy captured (C6) and missing modality handling recorded (C7).
- Validation scheme and setting recorded (D3–D5) and split unit captured when stated (D4).
- Robot/HRI context recorded where applicable (D6–D8).
- Any confusion matrix/prediction outputs pasted verbatim (D9) with locator in Outcome_Notes.
- Quality checklist Q1–Q9 scored (0/1/2) with notes for borderline items; Quality_Total left to formula/lead computation as specified.
- Reviewer_Comments includes any ambiguities needing team attention.
- Synthesis stratification coding fields (Section F: F1–F4) completed as best as possible (or Unclear + note).

8) Version history

- v3.0 (2026-02): Aligned with OSF protocol v2.1; adds preregistered synthesis stratification fields (TaskType, EmotionType, FuzzyRole, Evidence) and CORE vs EXTENDED handling; expands HRI context capture; refines controlled vocabularies; retains no-derived-metrics rule and reliability check procedure.
- v3.0 Gold Standard (2026-02): Integrates clarity refinements (TaskType 'Other' examples; explicit Split_Unit definitions; clarified C5 vs F3 relationship; anchored example for Evidence 'limited comparability'; reinforced 'do not assign CORE/EXTENDED during extraction') and integrates the v2.1 quality checklist Q1–Q9 with scoring guidance and Quality_Total computation.
- v2.0 (2025-09-19): Clarified no derived calculations at extraction; elevated reliability subset to 20–25% with κ /ICC targets; refined controlled vocabularies; added formatting rules and minimal checklist.
- v1.0 (2025-06-18): Initial release.